

Spatial Patterns and Environmental Exposure to Groundwater Hardness Levels Across Localities in Dutsinma Town, Katsina State, Nigeria

C. Akawu

University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria

N.R. Oluyori

University of Abuja, Nigeria

T.K. Oyatayo ✉

Kwararafa University, Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

C. Ndabula

Federal University Dutsinma, Katsina State, Nigeria

G.G. Jidauna

Federal University Dutsinma, Katsina State, Nigeria

Abstract

Studies on water quality have placed very little attention on water hardness, just because of the widely held impression that it poses no health risks except at very extreme levels. However, it affects the day-to-day life of the household in a number of ways, causing diverse damages and compromising household wellbeing. This study approached the spatial analysis and exposure to groundwater hardness using a hydro-geomorphological framework of intensity, extent and frequency/rate. A combination of purposive and stratified sampling techniques was used to collect groundwater samples from wells and boreholes based on the localities that characterise the growth and morphological development of Dutsinma town. Both Ca and Mg ions were determined using the Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS), while Cl and SO₄ ions were determined using the turbidimetric method. These were expressed as hardness in mg/l CaCO₃ by the calculation method. Results revealed that Calcium hardness is more prevalent at higher mean levels (184mg/l CaCO₃) than Magnesium (67 mg/l CaCO₃), and the mean levels of CaH (184mg/l CaCO₃), TH (251 mg/l CaCO₃), and NCH (135 mg/l chlorides) are higher in boreholes than wells. All (100%) of groundwater sources in Zone A have hard to very hard degrees of hardness, and 61.11% in Zone B. In contrast, MgH recorded all (100%) sources in Zone B and Zone A (81.81%) as soft to moderate hardness. In terms of CH, 63.63% and 88.88% of sample sources showed hard to very hard groundwater in both Zone A and Zone B respectively. In contrast, 72.72% of sample sources in Zone A have hard to very hard levels of hardness, while 88.88% in Zone B have Soft to moderate hardness. Maps of hardness zones showed that about 12294 m² (57%) of the town is covered by hard to very hard groundwater hardness, and the remaining 43% (9356m²) is soft to moderately hard. Overall results revealed that there is widespread groundwater hardness in Dutsinma town. The public should be enlightened on this, and also on how they can, at the household level treat water hardness.

Keywords: *Groundwater, Hardness, Carbonate, Non-carbonate and calcium.*

Suggested citation: Akawu, C., Oluyori N.R., Oyatayo, T.K., Ndabula, C., & Jidauna, G.G. (2025). Spatial Patterns and Environmental Exposure to Groundwater Hardness Levels Across Localities in Dutsinma Town, Katsina State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(4), 12-26. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(4).02

Introduction

Groundwater is among the most critical natural and abundant resources and a main water supply source worldwide (Jidauna et al., 2013; Dandge & Patil, 2022). Water quality is a critical problem for human beings as it is closely related to human wellbeing (Balakrishnan, 2012; Dandge & Patil, 2022). Water quality and water supply have become a significant global problem as a consequence of enhanced population growth (Dandge & Patil, 2022) and the changing nature of water uses for industrial, agricultural, along other diverse applications and development (Awodumi & Akeasa, 2017).

Groundwater is a significant water-drinking source and has a very wide spectrum of domestic uses. Groundwater quality is of great significance due to its role as a key alternative source of domestic supply. The level of groundwater is decreasing gradually, due to over-exploitation; therefore, this is important to begin investigations concerned with groundwater qualification and quantification that are the main criteria to plan for its management and utilization (Pandian & Jeyachandran, 2014; Dandge & Patil, 2022). Shallow characters and high permeability of groundwater make them highly susceptible to pollution, and once the groundwater is contaminated, its quality cannot be restored easily (Pardo et al., 2000; Mahagamage & Manage, 2015; Jidauna et al., 2017). In most of the developing countries, rural and emerging and rapidly developing urban areas, their domestic water supply needs are dependent on groundwater by means of dug wells and boreholes.

Hardness, a physicochemical property of water, is generally a measure of calcium and magnesium cations in water (Ramya et al., 2024). Although other polyvalent cations such as Zinc, iron, strontium, aluminium, and manganese can also contribute to water hardness; however, they are generally present in very low concentrations (Kumari, 2016; Rahman, 2016; Ndabula et al., 2018).

The problems identified to necessitate this study include the fact that so much emphasis in the studies on water quality has been on drinking water and health effects, and since water hardness is not commonly associated with health problems except at very extreme hardness levels, it is relegated to the background. Also, not much has been appreciated to consider the diverse effects of water hardness associated with the wide range of domestic uses and the corresponding effects. Also, most researchers (Sabitri, 2010; Rahman, 2016; Jidauna et al., 2017; Nabula et al., 2018) have not approached this aspect of the study in the context of the degree of exposure of households based on the extent, frequency and magnitude of hard water on households and their varieties of domestic water uses. If we can accumulate these diverse effects and the frequency due to the multiplicity of domestic water uses, then we would know that indeed, water hardness is a serious water quality issue that should be given equal emphasis in research.

From geo-knowledge and observations in the study area, pipe-borne water is infrequent in supply. Also, the water board's water supply system has not been extended to most parts of the town that have emerged due to recent development. This problem is compounded by seasonal fluctuations in the dam storage due to low rainfall, which is characteristic of semi-arid areas and the complications caused by climate change regimes. The problem cannot be exempted from the increasing cost of processing raw water amidst poor government logistics. Therefore, reliance on groundwater is not left with an option. Unfortunately, this source of water has been reported to be hard. It has been observed that households or government, and even NGOs spent their hard-earned resources to dig wells or sink boreholes, only

to abandon them due to extreme saltiness or hardness. This is due to poor details on the spatial patterns of groundwater in the town.

Most households may only have the capacity for shallow wells but cannot afford boreholes. Therefore, reliance on public intake sources is predominant in the town (Ndabula et al, 2018). Moreover, the water supply from the water board has not been extended to most parts of the town.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is constructed on the environmental geomorphological principle of exposure as a function of extent, frequency and intensity, which are also the determinants of effects.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Local Government Area (LGA) of Katsina State lies between latitude 12° 0' 17.00"N to 12° 0' 17.84" N and longitude 007° 0' 26"E (Joseph, et al., 2018). It is bounded by Kurfi and Charanchi LGA to the North, Kankia LGA to the East, Safana and Dan-Musa LGA to the West, and Matazu LGA to the southeast, as shown in Figure 1 (Joseph et al., 2018). Dutsinma LGA covers an area of approximately 552,323 km² and had a population of around 169,829 according to the 2006 National Census. Most of the indigenous people are predominantly food crops and livestock farmers and traders. The coming of the Federal

University since 2011 to date has changed the socio-economic activities of the town and has recorded rapid urban development and expansion.

Climate

Katsina State has a tropical wet and dry climate, classified by Koppen as an Aw climate. The rainy season is from May to September, peaking in August. The area receives an average of about 700 mm of rainfall per year. However, the pattern of rainfall in the area is highly variable (Abaje, Sawa, & Ati, 2014). This can result in severe and widespread droughts that can impose serious socio-economic constraints (Abaje, Sawa, & Ati, 2014). The mean annual temperature ranges from 29 °C – 31 °C (Abaje, Sawa, & Ati, 2014). The highest air temperature normally occurs in April/May, and the lowest in December through February. Evapotranspiration is generally high throughout the year. The highest amount of evaporation occurs during the dry season. The area's vegetation is of the Sudan savanna type, combining characteristics and species from both the Guinea and Sahel savannas (Abaje, 2007; Tukur et al., 2013; Abaje, Sawa, & Ati, 2014).

a) b)
Figure 2 (a, b). Administrative Map of Katsina State
 Sources: El-ladan, I., & Maiwada, N. (2014)

Geology

Katsina State (figure 3) is predominantly underlain by the Basement Complex with 80% of its geology underlined by the Basement Complex of Nigeria which is characterized by Migmatite Gneiss, Metasediments and Old Granite known as Granite Suite (Ibrahim & Nurudeen 2014; Joseph, et al., 2018; Jidauna et al., 2023).

Sampling and Sample Collection Techniques

A combination of purposive and stratified sampling techniques was used. Groundwater samples were collected from predetermined wells and boreholes based on the localities that characterise the growth and morphological development of Dutsinma town. The town was geographically divided into the north (Zone A) and south (Zone B). Four (4) localities were selected in each zone as (A1, A2, A3 & A4) and

(B1, B2, B3 & B4) for the respective zones. A total of sixteen (16) water samples were collected, 8 from boreholes and 8 from wells, proportionally across the localities.

APHA (1995) Standard methods were used for sample collection and preservation from the field to the laboratory up to the point of analysis. All the water samples were collected aseptically into sterilized screw capped glass bottles and brought to the laboratory from the field (Ramya, et al., 2024). The GPS coordinates of the locations of boreholes and wells where samples were collected were recorded by GPS (Hand-held Garmin eTrex 30 GPS receiver).

Figure 3. Geologic Map of the Northern Katsina State Showing Dutsinma LGA

Source: adapted from GEO INVEST and BOREWELL NIG. LTD Katsina, Modified

Analysis and Classification of Various Hardness Levels

The CaH, MgH and TH levels/ concentrations were determined by the EDTA-Titrimetric method. The procedure was as follows;

50ml of water sample was measured and poured into a conical flask along with 100ml of ammonia buffer solution and 100-200 mg of Erichrome black- T indicator, followed by titration with EDTA solution present in a burette. The endpoint is noted down by a change of the water solution colour from wine red to blue and expressed as CaCO₃ equivalent in mg/l. The amount of Hardness in water is calculated by using the formula. Hardness as mg/l CaCO₃ = ml of EDTA solution used x1000/ Volume of water samples taken (ISO Standard Methods, 1998; Ramya et al., 2024). Sulphate and chloride concentrations were measured by Spectrophotometric (Spectro UV-VIS Double UVD 2960) methods

The *United States Geological Survey (USGS) scheme* for classification of hardness levels and intensity in CaCO₃ mg/l was adapted for this study. The four (4) classes are as follows;

0 - 60 (Soft; S)

61 – 120 (Moderately Hard; MH)

121 – 180 (Hard; H)

>180 (Very Hard; VH)

Analysis of the Rate of Prevalence of the Hardness Classes in (%) among Groundwater Sources in the Localities

The rate/frequency of prevalence of each of these classes of hardness levels was further analysed based on occurrence rate in % for each of the sample sources and zones. Percentage (%) rate of prevalence of

soft, moderately hard, hard and very hard in the sample localities; this will be performed for each of the hardness types: CaH, MgH, TH, CH and NCH, respectively.

Analysis of Spatial Extent of Groundwater Hardness for Each of the Hardness Levels

GIS analysis using ArcGIS, applied the Kriging interpolation techniques to map the town using hardness levels at well-spread point samples in the town. The extents of the hardness zones were then estimated in the spatial analyst tool.

Results and Discussions

This study revealed that there are clear patterns of variation in water hardness levels across the localities in Dutsinma town. Results of sample analyses showed hardness levels from soft to Very Hard at varying percentages.

Table 1. Water Hardness Levels of all Sampled Boreholes Across the Localities in Dutsinma Town

Sample	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	2HCO ₃ ⁻	CaH mg/l as CaCO ₃	MgH mg/l as CaCO ₃	TH mg/l as CaCO ₃	CH as CaCO ₃	NCH as Cl and SO ₄
A1BH	164	23	280	410	96	506	230	276
A2BH	91	23	190	228	96	324	156	168
A3BH	71	15	240	178	63	241	197	44
A4BH	692	64	280	1730	267	1997	230	1767
B1BH	77	14	440	193	58	251	361	110
B2BH	75	12	340	188	50	238	279	42
B3BH	8	12	210	20	50	70	172	102
B4BH	28	13	400	70	54	124	328	204
Mean				184	67	251	246	135

Source: Field work, 2025.

Based on the mean hardness values in Table 1. It revealed that CaH is more prevalent at higher levels (184 mg/l CaCO₃) than MgH (67 mg/l CaCO₃). MgH is not common, as results showed most sampled BH falling under soft to moderately hard limits. CH is also more prevalent at higher levels (246 mg/l) than NCH (135 mg/l). Inverse relationship between CaH and MgH in that where CaH is high, MgH is low. Similarly, with CH and NCH such that where CH is high, NCH is low and vice versa in the respective cases. An extreme outlier was observed in A4BH with very extreme CaH hardness level (1730mg/l CaCO₃) and NCH hardness level (1767mg/l CaCO₃). It is worth noting that some of the high variation in levels of CH might also be a signal of surface or subsurface pollution which is in line with Ndabula et al. (2018) and Jidauna et al. (2023) often possess health risk.

Table 2. Water Hardness Levels of all Sampled Wells Across the Localities in Dutsinma Town

Sample	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	2HCO ₃ ⁻	CaH mg/l as CaCO ₃	MgH mg/l as CaCO ₃	TH mg/l as CaCO ₃	CH as CaCO ₃	NCH as Cl and SO ₄
A1WL	108	18	640	270	75	345	525	180
A2WL	123	13	290	308	54	362	238	124
A3WL	57	26	400	143	108	251	328	77
A4WL	49	14	140	123	58	181	115	66
B1WL	58	22	220	145	92	237	180	57

B2WL	37	25	280	93	104	197	230	33
B3WL	29	5	260	73	21	94	213	119
B4WL	8	10	170	20	42	62	139	77
Mean	59	17	300	147	69	216	246	92

Source: Field work, 2025.

The observations in Table 2 are similar to those in Table 1. Except that CH is observed to be prevalent in some sampled wells than in BH. Possible surface pollution through seepage or infiltration. Also, the unusual extreme CaH and NCH observed in A4BH are not seen in the corresponding A4WL and are almost soft in NCH.

Table 3. Summary of Mean Values of Hardness between Boreholes and Wells

Sample Source	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	2HCO ₃ ⁻	CaH mg/l as CaCO ₃	MgH mg/l as CaCO ₃	TH mg/l as CaCO ₃	CH as CaCO ₃	NCH as Cl and SO ₄
BH	74	16	237	184	67	251	246	135
WL	59	17	300	147	69	216	246	92

Source: Field work, 2025.

From Table 3. Above, it shows that the mean levels of CaH (184mg/l CaCO₃), TH (251 mg/l CaCO₃) and NCH (135 mg/l chlorides) are higher in BH than WL. This may be attributed to the deeper underlying bedrock.

Table 4a. Results of Spatial Analysis of the Rate of Prevalence of Calcium Hardness Levels across the Northern Localities (ZONE A) in Dutsinma Town

Localities	Soft (%)	Moderate Hardness (%)	Hard (%)	Very Hard (%)
Zone A: Northern Ward	00.00	00.00	27.00	73.00
A1:Doroyi/Abuja Road	00.00	00.00	00.00	100.00
A2: Yandaka	00.00	00.00	00.00	100.00
A3: Low-cost/Wakaji	00.00	00.00	100.00	00.00
A4: Hayin Gada	00.00	33.33	00.00	66.66

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table 4b. Results of Spatial Analysis of the Rate of Prevalence of Calcium Hardness Levels across the Southern Localities (ZONE B) in Dutsinma Town

Localities	Soft (%)	Moderate Hardness (%)	Hard (%)	Very Hard (%)
Zone B: Southern Ward	33.33	33.33	11.11	22.22
B1: Kadangaru	00.00	00.00	50.00	50.00
B2: Dan-Rimi/Tsamiya	33.33	33.33	00.00	33.33
B3: Dogon Karfe/Doctor Campus	50.00	50.00	00.00	00.00
B4:S-Qtrs/Dangaje/Science/S-Rima	50.00	50.00	00.00	00.00

Source: Field work, 2025.

Results as presented in Tables 4a and 4b are as follows: Calcium Hardness (CaH): about 72.72% of all sampled areas in this ward showed very high levels of CaH, while the remaining 27.27% high levels of CaH. This implies that all (100%) sources of domestic water in this ward range between high to very high

levels of CaH. In fact, in Zone A1 and A2 (Doroyi/Abuja road & Yandaka), all (100%) of the sources recorded very high CaH levels, while in Zone A3 (Lowcost/wakaji), all (100%) sources recorded high hardness levels. Zone A4 (Hayin Gada) about 66.66% showed very high CaH levels, and the remaining 33.33% moderate CaH levels. When compared to the results of zone B (southern part of the town), which has only 22.22% of all sources with very high levels of CaH, 11.11% high hardness level, and the remaining 66.66% are between soft to moderate levels of CaH. This implies that CaH is more prevalent and in higher concentrations in zone A than zone B for all types of domestic water sources. As earlier discussed, this is more observed in underground sources, pointing to the fact that geologic factors account for more of this variation, which is line with results of Nabula et al. (2018).

Table 5a. Results of Spatial Analysis of the Rate of Prevalence of Magnesium Hardness Levels across the Northern Localities (ZONE A) in Dutsinma Town

Localities	Soft (%)	Moderate Hardness (%)	Hard (%)	Very Hard (%)
Zone A: Northern Ward	36.36	45.45	00.00	18.18
A1: Doroyi/Abuja Road	33.33	66.66	00.00	00.00
A2: Yandaka	66.66	33.33	00.00	00.00
A3: Low-cost/Wakaji	00.00	100.00	00.00	00.00
A4: Hayin Gada	33.33	00.00	00.00	66.66

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table 5b. Results of Spatial Analysis of the Rate of Prevalence of Magnesium Hardness Levels across the Southern Localities (ZONE B) in Dutsinma Town

Localities	Soft (%)	Moderate Hardness (%)	Hard (%)	Very Hard (%)
Zone B: Southern Ward	77.77	22.22	00.00	00.00
B1: Kadangaru	50.00	50.00	00.00	00.00
B2: Dan-Rimi/Tsamiya	66.66	33.33	00.00	00.00
B3: Dogon Karfe/Doctor Campus	100.00	00.00	00.00	00.00
B4: S-Qtrs/Dangaje/Science/S-Rima	100.00	00.00	00.00	00.00

Source: Field work, 2025.

Magnesium Hardness (MgH) as shown in Tables 5a and 5b indicated that MgH is generally not common, as most of the sources (45.45%) showed only moderate MgH and 36.36% are soft, with only 18.18% having very high MgH levels in zone A. Similarly, in zone B, about 77.77% of sources are soft and only 22.22% recorded moderate levels of MgH. At least, Zone A recorded about 18.18% of sources having Very Hard MgH compared to Zone B, where all (100%) are Soft.

The principal sources of these two cations, calcium and magnesium, are sedimentary rocks, seepage, and runoff from soils. Since the study area is not underlain by sedimentary formation, seepage and runoff from soils are the probable causes. Groundwater is harder than surface water because of the higher solubilising potential of groundwater over surface water towards soils or rocks containing minerals like calcite, dolomite and gypsum (Sabitri, 2010; Singh, 2021).

Table 6a. Results of Spatial Analysis of the Rate of Prevalence of Total Hardness Levels across the Northern Localities (ZONE A) in Dutsinma Town

Localities	Soft (%)	Moderate Hardness (%)	Hard (%)	Very Hard (%)
Zone A: Northern Ward	00.00	00.00	00.00	100.00
A1: Doroyi/Abuja Road	00.00	00.00	00.00	100.00

A2: Yandaka	00.00	00.00	00.00	100.00
A3: Low-cost/Wakaji	00.00	00.00	00.00	100.00
A4: Hayin Gada	00.00	00.00	00.00	100.00

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table 6b. Results of Spatial Analysis of the Rate of Prevalence of Total Hardness Levels across the Southern Localities (ZONE B) in Dutsinma Town

Localities	Soft (%)	Moderate Hardness (%)	Hard (%)	Very Hard (%)
Zone B: Southern Ward	22.22	22.22	11.11	44.44
B1: Kadangaru	00.00	00.00	00.00	100.00
B2: Dan-Rimi/Tsamiya	33.33	00.00	00.00	66.66
B3: Dogon Karfe/Doctor Campus	00.00	100.00	00.00	00.00
B4:S-Qtrs/Dangaje/Science/S-Rima	00.00	50.00	50.00	00.00

Source: Field work, 2025.

Total Hardness (TH): It was striking to observe that all (100%) of the water sources in zone A have very high levels of TH, while in zone B, only 44.44% with the remaining 11.11%, 22.22% and 22.22% as high, moderate and soft respectively. This is also due to geological factors, as underground water sources are the major source of very high TH levels as observed and agrees with the findings of Jidauna et al. (2017) and Ndabula et al. (2018).

Table 7a. Results of Spatial Analysis of the Rate of Prevalence of Carbonate Hardness Levels across the Northern Localities (ZONE A) in Dutsinma Town

Localities	Soft (%)	Moderate Hardness (%)	Hard (%)	Very Hard (%)
Zone A: Northern Ward	00.00	36.36	09.09	54.54
A1: Doroyi/Abuja Road	00.00	33.33	00.00	66.66
A2: Yandaka	00.00	33.33	33.33	33.33
A3: Low-cost/Wakaji	00.00	00.00	00.00	100.00
A4: Hayin Gada	00.00	66.66	00.00	33.33

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table 7b. Results of Spatial Analysis of the Rate of Prevalence of Carbonate Hardness Levels across the Southern Localities (ZONE B) in Dutsinma Town

Localities	Soft (%)	Moderate Hardness (%)	Hard (%)	Very Hard (%)
Zone B: Southern Ward	11.11	00.00	33.33	55.55
B1: Kadangaru	00.00	00.00	50.00	50.00
B2: Dan-Rimi/Tsamiya	33.33	00.00	00.00	66.66
B3: Dogon Karfe/Doctor Campus	00.00	00.00	50.00	50.00
B4:S-Qtrs/Dangaje/Science/S-Rima	00.00	00.00	50.00	50.00

Source: Field work, 2025.

Regarding results as presented in Tables 7a and 7b above, it is indicated that Carbonate Hardness (CH) varies between zones and B. About 54, 54% and 55.55% of all sources in both zone A and B recorded very high levels of CH. About 33.33% of sources in zone B also recorded high CH levels compared to 09.09% in zone A, although, 36.36% of sources in zone A have moderate CH levels compared to 0% in zone B which also has at least 11.11% sources that are soft compared to Zone A with 0% sources of soft water. It can generally be deduced that CH is almost evenly distributed between Zone A and Zone B.

Table 8a. Results of Spatial Analysis of Groundwater Non-Carbonate Hardness Levels across the Northern Localities (ZONE A) in Dutsinma Town

Localities	Soft (%)	Moderate Hardness (%)	Hard (%)	Very Hard (%)
Zone A: Northern Ward	09.09	18.18	45.45	27.27
A1: Doroyi/Abuja Road	00.00	00.00	66.66	33.33
A2: Yandaka	00.00	00.00	100.00	00.00
A3: Low-cost/Wakaji	33.33	66.66	00.00	00.00
A4: Hayin Gada	00.00	33.33	00.00	66.66

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table 8b. Results of Spatial Analysis of the Rate of Prevalence of Non-Carbonate Hardness Levels across the Northern Localities (ZONE A) in Dutsinma Town

Localities	Soft (%)	Moderate Hardness (%)	Hard (%)	Very Hard (%)
Zone B: Southern Ward	44.44	44.44	00.00	11.11
B1: Kadangaru	50.00	50.00	00.00	00.00
B2: Dan-Rimi/Tsamiya	100.00	00.00	00.00	00.00
B3: Dogon Karfe/Doctor Campus	00.00	100.00	00.00	00.00
B4:S-Qtrs/Dangaje/Science/S-Rima	00.00	50.00	00.00	50.00

Source: Field work, 2025.

Non-Carbonate (Permanent) Hardness (NCH): About 72% of all sampled sources in zone A and only 11.11% in zone B recorded high to very high levels of NCH. On the other hand, about 44.44% of all sources in zone B have soft levels of NCH compared to only 09.09% in zone A. This implies that NCH is predominant in Zone A than Zone B.

Table 9. Summary of Rate (%) of Occurrence of Various Forms and Intensities of Hardness in Zone A and Zone B

ZONE	Hardness type	Soft (%)	Moderate Hardness (%)	Hard (%)	Very Hard (%)
	CaH				
A		00.00	00.00	27.00	73.00
B		33.33	33.33	11.11	50.00
	MgH				
A		36.36	45.45	00.00	18.18
B		77.77	22.22	00.00	00.00
	TH				
A		00.00	00.00	00.00	100.00
B		22.22	22.22	11.11	44.44
	CH				
A		00.00	36.36	09.09	54.54
B		11.11	00.00	33.33	55.55
	NCH				
A		09.09	18.18	45.45	27.27
B		44.44	44.44	00.00	11.11

Source: Field work, 2025.

The outcome of CaH as observed in sample sources and as presented in Table 9. Above, it clearly shows that all (100%) of the groundwater sources in Zone A have hard to Very Hard degrees of hardness and also many (61.11%) in Zone B. In contrast, MgH recorded all (100%) sources in Zone B and Zone A (81.81%) as soft to moderate hardness, while 18.18% of sources recorded Very Hard MgH. With regards

to TH, most (55.55%) have Hard to Very Hard degrees of hardness, while 44.44% have soft to moderate degrees of hardness in Zone B. On the other hand, all (100%) of the sampled sources in Zone A have Very Hard degrees of hardness.

In terms of CH, 63.63% and 88.88% of sample sources showed Hard to Very Hard groundwater in both Zone A and Zone B, respectively. In contrast, 72.72% of sample sources in Zone A have hard to Very Hard levels of hardness, while 88.88% in Zone B have Soft to Moderate Hardness.

Spatial Zones and Extents of Groundwater Hardness in Localities of Dutsinma Town

Hardness zones points of the various forms of groundwater hardness were developed as shown below:

Figure 4. Calcium Hardness Zones in Dutsinma Town
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 5. Magnesium Hardness Zones in Dutsinma Town
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 6. Total Hardness Zones in Dutsinma Town
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 7. Carbonate Hardness Zones in Dutsinma Town
Source: Field Survey, 2024

From Fig.5, it shows that almost everywhere is occupied by hard to very hard groundwater Carbonate. This is regarded as temporary hardness. This form of hardness, luckily, can easily be treated by boiling the water. By this, soluble bicarbonates are converted into insoluble carbonates, which are removed by filtration.

By Clark's Method:

Calcium hydroxide is Clark's reagent. It removes the hardness of water by converting bicarbonates into carbonates.

Figure 8. Non-Carbonate Hardness Zones in Dutsinma Town
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 8 shows that non-carbonate hardness is higher in the southern localities of the town, as occupied by hard to very hard groundwater. While the northern except for some small patches, is mainly occupied by soft to moderately hard groundwater. This implies that the soluble salts of magnesium and calcium are present in the form of chlorides and sulfides in water. We call it permanent hardness because this hardness cannot be removed by boiling (BYJU'S, n.d.). We can remove this hardness by treating the water with washing soda (lime). Insoluble carbonates are formed when washing soda reacts with the sulphide and chloride salts of magnesium and calcium, and thus, hard water is converted to soft water (BYJU'S, n.d.). Other methods include;

- Gan's Permutit Method:

In this method, sodium aluminium ortho silicate, known as permutit or zeolite, is used to remove the permanent hardness of the water (Cheruiyot, 2023).

- Calgon's Process:

In this method, sodium-hexa-meta-phosphate (NaPO_3)₆, known as Calgon, is used. The hardness in water is removed by the adsorption of Ca^{++} and Mg^{++} ions (Cheruiyot, 2023).

- Ion Exchange Resin Method:

In this method, the permanent hardness of water is removed by using resins (Cheruiyot, 2023). $\text{Ca}^{++}/\text{Mg}^{++}$ ions are exchanged with Cl^- , and SO_4^{-2} ions are exchanged with anion exchange resin (RNH_2OH). Demineralised water is formed in this process.

Table 8. Spatial Extents (m²) of the Various Hardness Zones Across the Localities in Dutsinma Town

	AREA (m ²)				
	Soft	Mod.Hard	Hard	Very Hard	Total
CaH	716	11908	8828	199	21650
MgH	13079	8573	0	0	21650
TH	60	912	14139	6539	21650
CH	56	113	697	20784	21650
NCH	979	8378	7341	4953	21650

Source: Field work, 2025.

From Table 8. It shows that a greater extent (11908 m²) of the town has moderately hard groundwater, followed by Hard with an extent of 8878 m². MgH is rare, with the whole extent of the town having soft to moderately hard groundwater. CH is widely spread, covering almost the whole town (20784m² or 96%). About 12294 m² (57%) of the town is covered by hard to very hard groundwater hardness, and the remaining 43% (9356m²) is soft to moderately hard.

Conclusion

The present study revealed extreme degrees of groundwater hardness all across the localities in Dutsinma town. The hydro-geomorphic framework that was used to approach this study helps in providing new forms of details in the water hardness literature. For instance, the intensity/levels of hardness were determined and classified into soft, moderately hard, hard, and very hard. The approach also provided the rate of prevalence in (%) of the various hardness levels among groundwater sources across the localities. Finally, the approach provided hardness zone maps, which were used to determine the spatial extent of groundwater hardness distribution in the various localities.

Recommendations

So it would be better if we bring awareness among the public on these patterns of hardness distribution and how to approach this base on households and communities or localities. Also, the hardness zone maps provided in this analysis could serve as a guide for site suitability decisions before investing in any

groundwater supply facilities. The diverse forms of hardness and their spatial patterns can be used to develop simple models of hard water treatment based on which form is prevalent in the localities.

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